

TITLE: The genetic basis of plumage coloration and elevation adaptation in a clade of recently diverged alpine and arctic songbirds

Supplemental Text S1. Tests for genetic associations with body color were largely confounded by noise, due either to sample size, or population structure. While this limits any confident conclusions regarding candidate loci, we note that significantly associated SNPs were located in or near 44 genes with previously described roles in melanin pigmentation (Baxter et al. 2019). This list includes the melanosomal transmembrane protein (*Oca2*) and solute carrier family 45 member 2 (*Slc45a2*), which both influence melanin-based plumage patches in capuchino seedeaters (*Sporophila* spp.) (Estalles et al. 2022). In particular, four of the most strongly associated SNPs are intron variants of nuclear factor I B (*Nfib*; Z chromosome). *Nfib* was found to play an important role in the coordination of stem cell behavior in mice, specifically in melanocyte stem cell proliferation and differentiation in hair follicles (Chang et al. 2013). Additionally, our analysis revealed a missense mutation in coatmer protein complex subunit beta 2 (*Copb2*), a gene also suggested to play a role in melanin pigmentation. Though specifically described in melanophores (Coutinho et al. 2004), it may play a similar role in organisms with melanocytes.